

ON THE STUDY OF REMOVAL OF RARE-EARTHS AND UX_1 FROM BERYLLIUM, ALUMINIUM, ZIRCONIUM AND URANIUM

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An attempt has been made to remove rare-earths and UX_1 from uranium, beryllium, aluminium and zirconium. The major constituents concerned containing rare-earths are taken in acetic acid solutions and solid calcium oxalate monohydrate is added and shaken for sometime. A decontamination of 1 p.p.m. is easily achieved after two or more successive operations. The method can be claimed to be free from any complexities mentioned earlier (*this Journal*, 1957, 34, 427).

In a previous communication (Purkayastha and Bhattacharyya, *this Journal*, 1957; 34, 427), it was observed that calcium oxalate acted as a faithful carrier of rare-earths and thorium activities. The authors added some calcium and precipitated it as oxalate in acetic acid medium. The precipitate was found to carry most of the rare-earths and thorium activities. This property was used by the authors for various purposes.

The present investigation relates to attempts to remove rare-earths and thorium (UX_1) from some of the important materials, used in nuclear science, by simply shaking with solid calcium oxalate monohydrate in acetic acid medium. This procedure may solve the complexities which was previously encountered in precipitation procedure and also bring out some improvements in the possibility of its application as a general technique in this type of investigation. It was anticipated that UX_1 could be made completely removable from aged uranyl nitrate solutions by mere shaking with $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$. This procedure guards against the possibility of carrying out trace of uranium along with calcium and may help us to proceed on with larger quantity of uranium for removal of UX_1 and rare-earth activities, which was not possible in the previous investigation. The extent to which $CaC_2O_4 \cdot H_2O$ goes into solution under experimental conditions and its removal from the parent uranyl ions in question are also the subject matter of study. With these objects in view, the present work was undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents used were mostly of AnalaR quality. Traces of iron from beryllium were removed by ether-extraction of the complex thiocyanate. Beryllium was then precipitated as hydroxide and dissolved in minimum quantity of HCl, which was then neutralised till precipitation. The precipitate of beryllium hydroxide was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and the medium was made 3N with respect to acetic acid.

In the case of zirconium, zirconium oxychloride was taken and dissolved in minimum quantity of HCl. It was then partially precipitated as hydroxide. The medium was made 3N with respect to acetic acid and kept for a few days till the precipitate went into solution.

In the cases of aluminium and uranium, the excess of mineral acid was neutralised and made 3*N* with respect to acetic acid. Uranyl nitrate used in removing UX₁ was of G.R.E. Merck quality.

Eu¹⁵⁴, Ca⁴⁵ and carrier-free Y⁹¹ were supplied by Harwell, England, as chloride in HCl solution.

The solution, prepared as described above, which contained the radioactive indicators concerned in the process at the start of the preparation, was shaken for about an hour with solid calcium oxalate monohydrate. The solid was separated from solution by centrifuging. The solid calcium oxalate was washed and dissolved in HCl and the activity carried by it was measured by a liquid counter. The solution was further treated with calcium oxalate monohydrate and the same procedure was repeated till it was in a sense free from any activity.

Decontamination was studied by varying the quantities of the major constituents and minor constituents, and consequently the quantities of the scavenger was also varied (Table I).

The data relating to the quantitative separation of UX₁ from uranium by mere shaking with CaC₂O₄, H₂O are recorded in Table II.

The extent to which calcium oxalate went into solution under such experimental conditions and its decontamination from a desired element (say uranium) were also studied (Table III).

TABLE I

Use of CaC₂O₄, H₂O in scavenging rare-earths from beryllium, aluminium, zirconium and uranium.

Major constituents in mg./50 c.c. (M).	CaC ₂ O ₄ .H ₂ O.	Minor constituents (in g./50 c.c.) (R).	Initial ratio (M:R).	M:R in soln. after subsequent shaking with CaC ₂ O ₄ , H ₂ O in operation number.				
				1.	2.	3.	4.	
Be	350	550 mg.	1 × 10 ⁻⁴ Y	1:2.8 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:1.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:7 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:1.7 × 10 ⁻⁷	
	700	820	1 × 10 ⁻⁴ Y	1:1.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:7.7 × 10 ⁻⁷	1:8.4 × 10 ⁻⁹	...	
	700	1800	3 × 10 ⁻⁴ Eu	1:4.3 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:1.3 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:1.1 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:2.2 × 10 ⁻⁷	
Al	300	930	1 × 10 ⁻⁴ Y	1:3.3 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:2.3 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:1 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:2.3 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:2.4 × 10 ⁻⁵
	600	840	1 × 10 ⁻⁵ Y	1:1.6 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:5.8 × 10 ⁻⁷	1:1.4 × 10 ⁻⁸	...	
	600	2000	3 × 10 ⁻⁴ Eu	1:50 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:1.7 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:5.9 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:1.1 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:4.4 × 10 ⁻⁷
Zr	300	840	1 × 10 ⁻⁴ Y	1:3.3 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:9.8 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:2.5 × 10 ⁻⁷	...	
	300	840	1 × 10 ⁻⁵ Y	1:3.3 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:5.9 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:2.5 × 10 ⁻⁵	...	
	600	1600	3 × 10 ⁻⁴ Eu	1:50 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:4.7 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:4.8 × 10 ⁻⁸	1:1.3 × 10 ⁻⁷	
*U	600	1400	1 × 10 ⁻³ Y	1:1.6 × 10 ⁻³	1:8.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:1.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:1.6 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:4 × 10 ⁻⁴
	600	1200	1 × 10 ⁻⁴ Y	1:1.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:10 × 10 ⁻⁶	1:3 × 10 ⁻⁷	...	
	1200	2400	3 × 10 ⁻⁴ Eu	1:2.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	1:3.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:4.1 × 10 ⁻⁵	1:4.3 × 10 ⁻⁷	

* In case of uranium, UX₁ was previously separated and necessary precautions were taken to guard against any activity due to disintegration of U₁.

TABLE II

Decontamination of calcium from uranium by successive precipitation of uranium with CO_2 -free NH_3 .

Ca/U in soln. at the start.	Ratio of Ca/U in the precipitate in operation		
	No. 1.	No. 2.	No. 3.
1:20	$1:2 \times 10^3$	$1:1.5 \times 10^3$	$1:1 \times 10^4$

TABLE III

Removal of thorium (UX_1) from uranium.

Uranium.	Inactive Th added.	CaC_2O_4, H_2O added.	% Removal or carrying in successive operations.					
			1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.
(1) 600 mg.	Nil	1.4 g.	91.0	10.0	0.002	...	...	...
(2) 2000	Nil	4.0	99.9	1.5	0.1	...	...	...
*(3) 600	1 mg.	1.6	37.0	0.28	0.25	10	0.02	0.001

* With appreciable amount of carrier added, decontamination becomes less sharp and it requires more successive operations than those in the previous case. The poor decontamination is presumably due to the complex oxalate ion-formation.

Ca^{45} was used as a radioactive indicator in the study of its decontamination. The oxalate ions were decomposed by nitric acid and the simple procedure of removing calcium from uranium by successive precipitation of uranium with CO_2 -free NH_3 was taken recourse to. The results of our investigation are given in tabular forms.

DISCUSSION

In the previous communication (*loc.cit.*), the carrying of rare-earths by calcium oxalate monohydrate was studied by simple precipitation. The major constituents were carried by co-precipitating with CaC_2O_4, H_2O . The results are very encouraging with small quantities of the elements to be decontaminated. This is, however, not practicable nor economic with larger quantities, and also it involves more chemical operations.

The procedure, adopted by us, for removing rare-earths and thorium from the elements such as beryllium, aluminium, zirconium and uranium by mere shaking with solid calcium oxalate monohydrate, is free from any complexity. It requires minimum chemical operations in the procedure. In some aspects, it may be more convenient than the solvent extraction and other procedures which are used in separating rare-earths from the materials mentioned above, because here the minor constituents are being separated and the major ones remain in a convenient form.

It is also interesting to note that the quantitative removal of UX_1 from uranium without any appreciable uranyl ion adsorbed is a troublesome problem with respect

to larger quantity in the previous precipitation procedure, but this type of simple shaking procedure, as described by us, with solid calcium oxalate monohydrate does not seem to carry uranium to any considerable extent even in high concentration of uranyl ion.

It has been observed by us, specially in the case of uranium, that during operation a certain amount of calcium goes into the solution. A simple method of calcium and uranium separation was taken recourse to. Table III shows that the amount of calcium remaining is negligibly small. Uranium, thus freed from rare-earths and thorium, can be safely recommended for nuclear researches.

We have only attempted a simple method to separate calcium from uranium. Any other modern procedure may also be used in case of each of the elements from which rare-earths have been eliminated. One of the advantages of the method is that UX_1 can be safely and quantitatively removed from uranium, and the separation of calcium from uranium is, however, a simple issue.

Thanks of the authors are due to Prof. B. D. Nagchaudhury for his keen interest in the work of this division.

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Received March 7, 1958.